

pH-metric investigation on binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with maleic acid in SLS-water mixtures

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Abstract : The formation constants of binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with maleic acid in (0.0–2.5% w/v) sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS)-water mixture were determined pH metrically at 303.0 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³. The existence of various binary complexes was established from modeling studies using the computer program MINIQUAD75. The best fit chemical models were arrived at based on the statistical parameters like crystallographic *R* factor and sum of squares of residuals in mass-balance equations. The trend in the variation of stabilities of binary complexes with change in the mole fraction of the medium was explained based on electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. The distribution diagrams of the complex species are also presented.

Keywords : Binary complexes, maleic acid, formation constants, sodium lauryl sulphate, pH-metric.

Introduction

The chemical speciation of elements in aquatic environments is one of the most important topics in the fields of analytical chemistry, geochemistry, toxicology and environmental chemistry. Chemical speciation is essential for discussing the chemical reactivity of trace constituents in the environment, such as biological availability and toxicity, and the geochemical behavior of chemical species. The term “chemical speciation” has been defined in IUPAC Recommendations 2000¹. In this recommendation, the term “chemical species” is utilized as a specific form of an element : isotopic composition, electronic or oxidation state, and complex or molecular structure. “Speciation analysis” is an analytical process for identifying and/or measuring the quantities of one or more individual chemical species in a sample, and “speciation of an element” implies to know the distribution of an element amongst defined chemical species in a system.

The purpose of this study is to confirm the species formed under the present experimental conditions and to validate the models by statistical treatment of the data.

The effect of medium on the chemical speciation of the complexes and the influence of errors in ingredients the magnitudes of stability constants are also studied. Hence, the stability constants of the binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} have been determined using pH metry. These values are potentially useful to environmental and biological problems²⁻⁴.

Experimental

Materials :

Maleic acid (E. Merck, Germany) solution (0.05 mol L⁻¹) was prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid concentration to increase the solubility. SLS (Merck, India) was used as received. 2 mol L⁻¹ sodium nitrate (Qualigens, India) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. 0.1 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solutions of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and 0.05 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solution of Hg^{II} nitrates were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple-distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the

errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification⁵⁻⁸. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{9,10}.

Apparatus :

The titrimetric data were obtained using ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01), which was calibrated with 0.05 mol L⁻¹ potassium hydrogen phthalate in acidic region and 0.01 mol L⁻¹ borax solution in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred SLS-water mixture containing the inert electrolyte. All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of SLS-water mixtures (0.0–2.5% w/v) by maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium nitrate at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. The effect of variation in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode was accounted for in the form of correction factor^{11,12}.

Procedure :

For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. Then the calomel electrode was refilled with SLS-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 mL. Titrations with different metal to ligand ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75, 1 : 5) were carried out with 0.40 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. The analytical concentrations of the ingredients are given in Table 1. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹³.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD¹⁴⁻¹⁶ was used to calculate the correction factor. By using the pH-metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75¹⁷, which exploit the advantage of the constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and the protonation constants of maleic acid were fixed. The variation of stability

Table 1. Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) of titrands in SLS-water mixtures

[NaOH] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³; V₀ = 50.0 cm³; temp. = 303 K; ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³; mineral acid = 1 mmol

% w/v	TMO			TL0 (Mal)	TL0 : TMO
	Pb ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Hg ^{II}		
0.0	0.1043	0.1013	0.1002	0.2498	2.50
				0.3747	3.75
				0.4996	5.00
0.5	0.1043	0.1013	0.1002	0.2493	2.50
				0.3739	3.75
				0.4986	5.00
1.0	0.1043	0.1013	0.1002	0.2483	2.50
				0.3724	3.75
				0.4966	5.00
1.5	0.1043	0.1013	0.1002	0.2494	2.50
				0.3741	3.75
				0.4988	5.00
2.0	0.1043	0.1013	0.1002	0.2488	2.50
				0.3732	3.75
				0.4976	5.00
2.5	0.1043	0.1013	0.1002	0.2478	2.50
				0.3717	3.75
				0.4956	5.00

constants with the mole fraction of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds on the basis of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The results of the final best-fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 2. Very low-standard deviation in overall stability constants (log β) signifies the precision of these constants. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ingredients at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems are validated by the residual analysis¹⁸.

Residual analysis :

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian or normal distribution. When

Table 2. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}-maleic acid complexes in SLS-water mixtures

SLS % (w/v)	log β _{mlh} (SD)			pH-range	NP	U _{corr}	χ ²	Skewness	Kurtosis	R-factor
	ML ₂	ML ₂ H	ML ₃							
Pb ^{II}										
0.0	6.65(25)	11.61(27)	10.15(23)	2.8–7.7	41	22.11	116.41	4.11	20.90	0.0498
0.5	6.83(06)	11.53(18)	9.50(19)	3.6–5.5	18	0.66	5.85	0.04	4.66	0.0088
1.0	6.73(20)	11.30(22)	9.60(23)	3.6–5.2	18	6.66	10.59	0.60	3.18	0.0246
1.5	7.10(25)	12.10(15)	10.50(24)	3.9–5.1	23	2.00	3.46	–0.13	2.62	0.0136
2.0	6.71(26)	11.65(26)	10.33(15)	4.1–5.2	18	0.66	9.41	0.76	5.95	0.0294
2.5	7.08(24)	11.91(24)	10.80(14)	3.8–5.1	18	6.00	6.58	–0.27	3.69	0.0248
Cd ^{II}										
0.0	6.76(18)	11.73(24)	10.32(12)	4.0–7.2	24	3.18	5.11	0.26	3.14	0.0152
0.5	6.65(13)	11.63(29)	9.34(28)	4.0–7.5	26	6.087	21.69	3.61	24.04	0.0265
1.0	6.41(19)	11.55(19)	9.33(12)	4.2–7.3	27	4.58	5.02	1.33	5.78	0.0228
1.5	6.33(18)	11.38(29)	9.43(21)	4.2–7.3	26	3.04	11.64	1.54	7.43	0.0195
2.0	6.76(25)	11.53(22)	9.84 (27)	4.2–7.3	22	6.84	9.64	0.25	5.39	0.0292
2.5	6.55(22)	11.32(23)	9.83(26)	4.2–7.4	22	4.21	3.82	–0.05	2.72	0.0223
Hg ^{II}										
0.0	6.93(26)	12.75(25)	9.35(29)	4.2–6.4	21	7.22	3.92	1.14	5.11	0.0291
0.5	6.58(22)	12.27(23)	9.22(24)	4.4–6.4	25	24.54	23.67	0.05	5.82	0.0587
1.0	6.36(24)	12.18(21)	9.36(23)	4.2–6.4	23	8.50	8.33	1.39	6.36	0.0344
1.5	6.69(25)	11.68(22)	9.39(24)	4.2–6.4	22	10.52	3.82	1.23	3.21	0.0378
2.0	6.39(26)	12.14(25)	9.22(26)	4.2–6.4	22	15.26	38.00	1.97	9.12	0.0456
2.5	6.25(22)	12.46(23)	9.12(24)	4.5–6.4	20	8.23	4.00	1.16	7.45	0.0325

$U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points; m = number of protonation constants; SD = Standard deviation.

the data are fit into the models, the residuals should ideally be equal to zero. If statistical measures of the residuals and the errors assumed in the models are not significantly different from each other, the model is said to be adequate. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis that the errors are random, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , Skewness, Kurtosis and R-factor. These statistical parameters show that the best-fit models portray the metal-ligand species in SLS-water mixtures, as discussed below.

In the present study, the χ^2 values are less than the table values, and so the models are accepted. The kurtosis values in this study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern. The values of skewness recorded in Table 2 are between –0.13 and 4.11 for Pb^{II}, –0.05 and 3.61 for Cd^{II} and 0.05 and 1.97 for Hg^{II}. These data evince that the residuals form part of a normal distribution. Hence, least square method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evi-

dent from crystallographic R-values. These statistical parameters thus show that the best-fit models portray the metal-ligand species in SLS media.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

In order to rely upon the best-fit chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was undertaken by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand, metal, log F and volume (Table 3). The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > metal > ligand > volume > log F. Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the suitability of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best-fit models.

Table 3. Effect of errors in influential parameters on Pb^{II}-maleic acid complex stability constants in 1.5% w/v SLS-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β _{mlh} (SD)		
		120	121	130
Acid	0	7.11(17)	12.10(18)	10.51(17)
	-5	Rejected	13.82(09)	12.88(08)
	-2	7.05(60)	12.90(08)	11.50(09)
	+2	6.78(16)	Rejected	9.56(39)
	+5	6.16(21)	Rejected	Rejected
Alkali	-5	5.69(40)	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	6.63(19)	Rejected	9.38(48)
	+2	Rejected	13.04(06)	11.75(05)
	+5	Rejected	14.00(14)	13.33(12)
Ligand	-5	6.82(86)	12.62(12)	11.24(13)
	-2	7.06(28)	12.33(15)	10.81(15)
	+2	7.05(15)	11.85(25)	10.19(22)
	+5	6.98(11)	11.21(73)	9.59(45)
Metal	-5	7.09(20)	12.12(18)	10.61(16)
	-2	7.10(18)	12.11(18)	10.54(16)
	+2	7.10(16)	12.09(17)	10.46(17)
	+5	7.10(15)	12.07(17)	10.40(18)
Volume	-5	7.06(19)	12.09(18)	10.49(17)
	-2	7.08(19)	12.11(18)	10.51(17)
	+2	7.12(17)	12.11(18)	10.53(17)
log F	+5	7.13(17)	12.13(18)	10.55(17)
	-5	7.04(16)	11.82(28)	10.29(21)
	-2	7.05(18)	11.99(21)	10.43(18)
	+2	7.12(20)	12.21(16)	10.63(16)
	+5	7.11(25)	12.33(15)	10.76(16)

Effect of solvent :

Many workers were opinion that both electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects should be considered even in the case of simple acido-basic equilibria; one dominates the other, depending upon the nature of solute and solvent¹⁹⁻²¹. The effect of surfactant on complex equilibria and apparent shift in the magnitude of stability constants in micellar media can be attributed²⁷ to the creation of a concentration gradient of proton between the interface and the bulk solution. The number of micelles increases with the concentration of surfactant, and oppositely charged ions are concentrated in the Stern layer²². The dielectric constant of the medium has a direct influence on the protonation-deprotonation equilibria^{23,24}. According to Born equation, the energy to electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant of medium²⁵. The variations in log β_s of complexes of maleic acid with mole fraction of SLS-

water mixtures are given in Fig. 1. The linear trend indicates that long range interaction between metal ion and ligand is electrostatic in nature. The deviation from linearity may be due to some contributions from non-electrostatic forces. The cation stabilizing nature of co-solvent, specific solvent-water interactions, charge dispersion and in some system interaction of co-solvent with solute also accounts for small deviation from a linear relationship. So complex formation is considered as competition between pure and solvated form of ligand and metal ion, solvent-solvent interaction, relative thermodynamic stability and kinetic lability.

Distribution diagrams :

Maleic acid is a bidentate ligand that has two dissociable (carboxyl groups) protons. The different forms of maleic acid are LH₂, LH⁻, and L²⁻ in the pH range < 4.0, 2.0–7.0 and > 5.0 respectively. Hence, the plausible binary metal-ligand complexes can be predicted from these data. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML₂, ML₂H, ML₃ for Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}. The formation of various maleic acid complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

Fig. 1. Variation of overall stability constant values of metal-maleic acid complexes with mole fraction ($n_x \times 10^3$) of SLS-water mixtures : (a) Pb^{II}; (b) Cd^{II}; (c) Hg^{II}; (■)log β_{ML₂}; (▲) log β_{ML₃}; (●) log β_{ML₂H}.

The species ML₂H₂, ML₃H₃⁻, ML₃H₂²⁻ could not be detected in the present study probably because they are formed at very low pH. Some typical distribution diagrams in SLS-water mixtures are shown in Fig. 2. They indicate that the binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} are formed in the pH range 3.0–7.5. The species ML₂H, ML₂, ML₃ are formed in the pH range of 3.0–7.0. ML₂H is formed at lower pH with higher percentage in case of lead and mercury [Equilibria (6), (7), (8) and (18)]. ML₂, ML₃ are simultaneously formed with the increasing pH. Successive deprotonation of ML₂H forms ML₂ beyond a pH 6.0. The concentration of ML₂H species decreased, while the concentration of ML₂ and ML₃ increased in the pH range 4.0–6.0 [Equilibria (9), (10) and (11)]. ML₃

formed at higher pH with high percentage [Equilibria (11), (17), (22) and (25)].

Structures of complexes :

Maleic acid acts as a bidentate ligand by using its two oxygen donor sites and the chelation results in highly stable seven membered rings (Fig. 3). Octahedral structures are proposed to the complexes of all the metal ions. The VSEPR theory suggests that Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes shall be octahedral because there are six outer electron pairs. This argument supports the structures of complexes proposed in Fig. 3.

Conclusions

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies of the speciation of binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with maleic acid in SLS-water mixture.

- (i) Maleic acid forms both protonated and unprotonated complexes under a pH range of 3.0–7.0.

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of maleic acid in 1.0% w/v SLS-water mixture : (a) Pb^{II}, (b) Cd^{II} and (c) Hg^{II}.

Fig. 3. Structure of maleic acid complexes where S is either solvent or water molecules.

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- (ii) The binary species formed due to the interaction of maleic acid with metals are PbL₂, PbL₂H, PbL₃, CdL₂, CdL₂H, CdL₃, HgL₂, HgL₂H and HgL₃. These models are validated by statistical treatment of data.
- (iii) The linear variation of stability constants as a function of dielectric constant of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.
- (iv) Some species are stabilized due to electrostatic interactions and some are destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant.
- (v) The order of ingredients influencing the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors in their concentrations is alkali > acid > ligand > metal > total volume > log *F*.

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